

The S-dynamics in generalized covariant Hamiltonian system

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Abstract

Since the S-dynamics as a grand-new dynamics has been naturally discovered, an attempt to deeply study the S-dynamics in the generalized covariant Hamiltonian system (GCHS) is made such as its properties and application for the quantum mechanics. We demonstrate a fact that the manifolds exist some properties such as wave-particle duality in quantum mechanics based on S-dynamics.

1 Introduction

To begin with the generalized Poisson bracket (GPB) that is defined as the bilinear operation

$$\{f, g\}_{GPB} = J_{ij} \partial_i f \partial_j g$$

where $\partial_i = \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i}$, structural matrix J satisfies antisymmetric $J_{ij} = \{x_i, x_j\}_{GPB} = -J_{ji}$. Generalized Hamiltonian system (GHS) is defined by generalized Poisson bracket (GPB)

$$\dot{x}_i = \frac{dx_i}{dt} = \{x_i, H\}_{GPB} = J_{ij} \frac{\partial H}{\partial x_j}, \quad x \in \mathbb{R}^m \quad (1)$$

Subsequently, [1] has further developed generalized structural Poisson bracket (GSPB) equipped with geometric bracket $G(s, f, H)$ (in this case for functions f, H) to define generalized covariant Hamilton system (GCHS) as a complete version of generalized Hamiltonian system.

In this paper, we further investigate the applications of the S-dynamics in the generalized covariant Hamiltonian system (GCHS), as [2] indicated, we build some new concepts based on the paper [2] for quantum mechanics, in particular, the geometric wave-particle duality. We state that geometric wave-particle duality completely relies on the structure of the manifolds.

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1.1 GSPB, GCHS, geometric bracket

In order to better understand the concept of the GCHS for the subsequent discussions, in this section, we briefly retrospect some basic concepts of entire framework of GCHS [1]. Let M be a smooth manifold and let s be a smooth real structural function on M which is completely determined by the structure of manifold M .

Theorem 1 (GSPB). [1] *The GSPB on M of two functions $f, g \in C^\infty(M, \mathbb{R})$ is defined as*

$$\{f, g\} = \{f, g\}_{GPB} + G(s, f, g)$$

for \mathbb{R}^r , the geometric bracket is

$$G(s, f, g) = f\{s, g\}_{GPB} - g\{s, f\}_{GPB}$$

in which s is structural function associated with M .

Note that the structural function associated with M is a scalar function, in general, it can be arbitrarily chosen, but for the real reality, it's chosen by precise manifolds. Intuitively, one can understand this defined formulation by noting that the second part, geobacket, can be partially treated as the second part of the geodesic equation, and in so doing will make it clear. The GSPB depends smoothly on both $\{f, g\}_{GPB}$ and the geobacket $G(s, f, g)$. Obviously, the geobacket $G(s, f, g)$ is necessary for a complete Hamiltonian system, as a result of the geobacket $G(s, f, g)$, it can be generally used to depict nonlinear system in a non-Euclidean space, and for general manifolds. As GSPB defined, the GCHS is completely assured and determined by the GSPB. Therefore, the GCHS can be distinctly obtained as follows.

Theorem 2 (GCHS). [1] *The GCHS on M of two functions $f, H \in C^\infty(M, \mathbb{R})$ is defined as*

$$\frac{Df}{dt} = \{f, H\} = \{f, H\}_{GPB} + G(s, f, H)$$

for \mathbb{R}^r , where geobacket in terms of f and Hamiltonian H is

$$G(s, f, H) = f\{s, H\}_{GPB} - H\{s, f\}_{GPB}$$

In fact, general covariance of the GCHS holds naturally. The GCHS is totally dependent on the GSPB and accordingly defined. Notice that the GCHS is covariant, it means that the GCHS is complete, and its form is invariant under the coordinate transformation, just like the covariance of the geodesic equation. So, the motion is completely determined by the structure of the manifold M . This is also like the idea of general relativity where particles move on geodesics and the bending is caused by the gravity.

Theorem 3 (TGHS, S-dynamics, GCHS). [1]

TGHS: $\frac{df}{dt} = \dot{f} = \{f, H\}_{GPB} - H\{s, f\}_{GPB}$.

S-dynamics: $\frac{ds}{dt} = w = \{s, H\}_{GPB} = \{1, H\}$.

GCHS: $\frac{Df}{dt} = \{f, H\} = \{f, H\}_{GPB} + G(s, f, H)$.

By defining the GSPB which can basically solve and describe an entire Hamiltonian system, even nonlinear system. Thus, in order to state this point. To start with, we recall the basic notions of the GSPB. We explain that the GCHS corresponds to non-Euclidean space which corresponds to curved coordinate systems in curved space-time. The geobacket $G(s, f, H)$ is the part that has been neglected for a long time which is rightly the correction term for the general covariance which certainly means nonlinear system. It is precisely because of the appearance of the second term $G(s, f, H)$ that the GCHS can describe and explain the generalized nonlinear system, the nonlinear Hamiltonian system.

In the following, the covariant equilibrium equation of the GCHS as a special case is naturally generated as follows.

Corollary 1. [1] *The covariant equilibrium equation of the GCHS is $\frac{\mathcal{D}f}{dt} = \{f, H\} = 0$ such that*

$$\{f, H\}_{GPB} + G(s, f, H) = 0$$

holds, where s is a structure function of the manifolds M , then f is called covariant conserved quantity.

Theorem 4. [1, 2] *There exists two different canonical Hamilton equations on manifolds respectively given by*

Canonical thorough Hamilton equations

$$\frac{dx_k}{dt} = \dot{x}_k = J_{jk}F_j, \quad \frac{dp_k}{dt} = \dot{p}_k = F_k$$

canonical covariant Hamilton equations

$$\frac{\mathcal{D}x_k}{dt} = \{x_k, H\}, \quad \frac{\mathcal{D}p_k}{dt} = \{p_k, H\}$$

where $\{\cdot, \cdot\} = \{\cdot, \cdot\}_{GPB} + G(s, \cdot, \cdot)$ is the GSPB, $D_i = \partial_i + \partial_i s$ is generalized derivative operators.

As we can see, there is a relation for canonical thorough Hamilton equations given by $\dot{x}_k = J_{jk}\dot{p}_j$.

Corollary 2. [2] *The ordinary time derivative d/dt and covariant time operator \mathcal{D}/dt can be respectively rewritten in a form*

$$d/dt = \dot{x}_i \partial_i$$

$$\mathcal{D}/dt = \dot{x}_i D_i$$

where \dot{x}_i is the TGHS in terms of x_i , and then for the generalized force field F , we get

$$dp_k/dt = F_k = \dot{x}_i \partial_i p_k = \dot{x}_i \xi_{ik}$$

in terms of the momentum, where $\partial_i p_k = \xi_{ik}$. Similarly, for the S-dynamics, it yields

$$ds/dt = w = \dot{x}_i \partial_i s = \dot{x}_i A_i \tag{2}$$

in terms of the structure function s , and the TGHS is given by

$$df/dt = \dot{x}_i \partial_i f$$

for any function f .

Note that the S-dynamics expressed by (2) implies the relation between the structure derivative A_i and the S-dynamics itself, the S-dynamics is only induced by the structure derivative A_i , and based on the manifolds itself.

1.2 Geospin variables

In this section, we simply review the mathematical formalism involved in [3], it shows that the equation of geodesics can be simplified by geospin matrix, in the case of Riemannian and pseudo-Riemannian manifolds.

Definition 1. [3] Let (M, g) be a Riemannian manifold, two kinds of geospin variables can be defined as

$$W_i^j = \Gamma_{ik}^j v^k, \quad W_{ik} = \Gamma_{ik}^j v_j \quad (3)$$

where v^j, v_j are the components of $v = v^j \frac{\partial}{\partial x^j} = v_j \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} = \frac{dx}{dt}$ respectively.

As geospin variables defined above, we mainly study the (1,1) form geospin variable W_i^j that relates to the geospin matrix W below.

Definition 2. The geospin matrix can be defined as $W = (W_j^k)$, where W_j^k are geospin variables.

Obviously, the symmetric holds $W_{kj} = W_{jk}$. The covariant derivative of a vector field v can be rewritten as follows

$$\nabla_k v^j = \frac{\partial v^j}{\partial x^k} + W_k^j, \quad \nabla_k v_j = \frac{\partial v_j}{\partial x^k} - W_{kj} \quad (4)$$

As a consequence, the geodesic for Riemannian manifolds can be rewritten in a compact and simple form by using the geospin matrix as follows:

$$\begin{cases} \frac{dx}{dt} = v \\ \frac{dv}{dt} = -Wv \end{cases}$$

This is a dynamic system.

1.3 S dynamics and geometrio on Riemannian manifold

Theorem 5 (Geometrio). [2] The structural operator \hat{S} can induce the following geometrio

$$\hat{S}(x_k, p_i, H)^T = (b_k, A_i, w)^T$$

in terms of position x_k , momentum p_i and Hamiltonian H respectively.

In other words,

$$\begin{aligned} Geo(x_k, p_i, H) &= \hat{S}(x_k, p_i, H)^T = (b_k, A_i, w)^T \\ &= (J_{ik}, 1, J_{ij} \partial_j H)^T \partial_i s \end{aligned}$$

We have given the geometrio in terms of the x_k, p_i, H respectively on the Riemannian manifold

$$Geo(x_k, p_i, H) = \hat{S}(x_k, p_i, H)^T = (b_k, A_i, w)^T$$

$$= \begin{pmatrix} J_{ik} \\ 1 \\ J_{ji}\partial_i H \end{pmatrix} \Gamma_{il}^l$$

The S dynamics on the Riemannian manifold (M, g) is given by the corollary below.

Corollary 3. [2] *The S dynamics on (M, g) is given by*

$$w = \hat{S}H(x) = J_{ij}\Gamma_{li}^l \frac{\partial H(x)}{\partial x_j}$$

where $\hat{S} = J_{ij}\Gamma_{li}^l \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j}$ is structural operator.

2 The S-dynamics

In this section, we will discuss how the S-dynamics works and its relation with the quantum mechanics, in particular, the wave-particle duality.

The S-dynamics as an independent part included in the GCHS is expressed by theorem 3

$$w = \{s, H\}_{GPB} = \{1, H\}$$

or (2) in corollary 2

$$ds/dt = w = \dot{x}_i A_i$$

where $\partial_i s = A_i$. In fact, (2) reveals the relation between the structural derivative A_i and the S-dynamics w which are directly induced by the structural function s on manifolds. In this paper, we mainly study these two functions, and denote by (A_i, w) .

Remark 1. *The S-dynamics w and structural derivative A_i are deduced by structural function s .*

$$(w, A_i)^T = (d/dt, \partial_i)^T s$$

where T means transposition of the matrix, and there is a relation $w = \dot{x}_i A_i$.

As the GCHS [1] already stated, the structural function s is only given by the structure of the manifolds, therefore, we have confidence to believe that (A_i, w) describes the dynamical characters of the manifolds. Inspired by the geometrio on the Riemannian manifold, we can surely take $A_i = \Gamma_{il}^l$, and then it implies that the structural function $s = \ln \sqrt{g}$ on Riemannian manifold [4-6], sometimes, $s = \ln \sqrt{-g}$ is chosen as needed.

Corollary 4. *The S-dynamics w and structural derivative A_i on Riemannian manifold are deduced by structural function $s = \ln \sqrt{g}$. Then*

$$(w, A_i)^T = (d/dt, \partial_i)^T \ln \sqrt{g}$$

where there is a relation $w = \dot{x}_i \Gamma_{il}^l$.

3 Geometric wave-particle duality

In this section, we give the application of S-dynamics in the GCHS to the quantum mechanics, more precisely, the wave-particle duality.

3.1 The geomentum and geomenergy

Definition 3 (Geometric wave-particle duality). *The geomentum $p^{(g)}$ and geomenergy function $E^{(g)}$ are respectively defined as*

$$\left(E^{(g)}, p^{(g)} \right)^T = \hbar(w, A)^T$$

for geometric wave-particle duality, where the components of the geomentum $p_i^{(g)} = \hbar A_i$, and \hbar is the Planck constant.

As a result, more precisely, geometric wave-particle duality is shown as

$$p_i^{(g)} = \hbar A_i, \quad E^{(g)} = \hbar w$$

Corollary 5. *The geomentum $p^{(g)}$ and geomenergy $E^{(g)}$ satisfies $E^{(g)} = \dot{x}_i p_i^{(g)}$.*

The corollary 5 implies that geometric wave-particle duality is strictly restrained in one formula which is a intrinsic dynamical property of the manifolds.

According to the geometrio 5, we get

$$\hbar \widehat{S}(x_k, p_i, H)^T = \hbar(b_k, A_i, w)^T = \left(\hbar b_k, p_i^{(g)}, E^{(g)} \right)^T$$

Theorem 6. *There exists geometric wave-particle duality such that corollary 5 holds for manifolds.*

Since the TGHS is $\dot{x}_k = J_{jk} F_j = J_{kj} D_j H$. Then, the S-dynamics can be specifically expressed as $w = \dot{x}_k A_k = J_{kj} \partial_j H A_k$. As we indicated, this is the relation between the TGHS and S-dynamics.

As corollary 3 shown, S dynamics on (M, g) is precisely written as

$$\begin{aligned} w &= \widehat{S}H(x) = J_{ij} \partial_i \ln \sqrt{g} \partial_j H(x) \\ &= \{ \ln \sqrt{g}, H(x) \}_{GPB} \end{aligned}$$

where structural operator $\widehat{S} = J_{ij} \partial_i \ln \sqrt{g} \partial_j$ on (M, g) .

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